

Bio-inspired nacre-like composites via simple, fast, and versatile techniques such as doctor-blading

M. Mirkhalaf¹, F. Barthelat^{1*}

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, McGill University, Montreal, Quebec, Canada

* Corresponding author (francois.barthelat@mcgill.ca)

Keywords: *Biomimetic composites, artificial Nacre, bio-inspiration*

1 Abstract

Theoretical and experimental studies show that the high performance of biological composites such as nacre and bone originates from a sophisticated microstructure, where hard and stiff inclusions form a staggered, brick wall-like structure within a softer and more deformable matrix. This morphology results in outstanding combinations of stiffness, strength and toughness, and therefore it is very attractive to duplicate it in engineering composites. Here, we demonstrate how simple, fast and versatile techniques such as doctor-blading can be used to make such bio-inspired composites. We fabricated and characterized composites made of micron-sized alumina tablets embedded in epoxy matrices. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) images show that the tablets are well dispersed, aligned, and staggered through the polymer matrix resulting in a nacre-like material. The tensile behavior of these composites shows a good combination of stiffness, strength and energy dissipation. We also developed finite element models of the staggered microstructure, which properly capture the interactions between inclusions and the effects of mineral concentration. These models can be used to optimize the microstructure and fully harness the nacre-like structure and mechanisms, in new materials with applications in aerospace, defense or biomedical engineering.

2 Introduction

The outstanding mechanical performance of nacre relies on its sophisticated and highly periodic brick wall-like microstructure. Duplicating such structures in synthetic materials represents tremendous challenges, and demands innovative fabrication techniques such as sequential Langmuir-Blodgett film/polymer deposition, layer by layer deposition,

sedimentation, and freeze-casting [1]. The design of these biomimetic materials starts by selecting the ingredients. The inorganic phase typically consists of nano-clays which bring stiffness and strength, while the organic matrix, mostly polymers, imparts ductility to the material. These methods are mostly either very slow processes or lack proper alignments of particles. They can also yield composite with only 10-20vol% [2], a low mineral content considering that hard biological composites contain up to 95vol% in nacre and 99vol% in enamel. In order to overcome these limitations, we have utilized fast and easy to implement fabrication methods such as doctor-blading to develop bio-inspired nacre-like composites. We have also used micrometer-sized alumina tablets as reinforcing agents which offer high stiffness and strength while being much easier to disperse compared to nano-clays.

3 Fabrication

A defined amount of alumina tablets (Antaria Limited, WA, Australia) was mixed into epoxy with 25wt% hardener (Buehler, ON, Canada), and sonication for one hour. The mixture was then applied onto a Teflon plate using a doctor-blade technique with a spatula. The shear and compression stresses applied onto the mixture in this process aligned the tablets in the polymer matrix resulting in a nacre-like morphology. Epoxy was then cured at room temperature for two days. The process yielded a 40mm x 15mm x 250 μ m film of composite. Fig. 1 shows a SEM image of the cross-section of the doctor-bladed epoxy/alumina composite with 35vol% mineral concentration. The inclusions showed very good dispersion of the inclusions, and a high degree of alignment, resembling the structure of natural nacre. At higher mineral concentrations the mixture was too viscous and broke during

doctor-blading so that the process was not successful.

4 Tensile tests

Tensile dog-bone samples were cut from the composite films, and tested in tension at a strain rate of 0.001/s using a miniature loading stage and in-situ imaging of the strain gage with a digital camera. The strains were measured by digital image correlation using commercial software VIC-2D. Tensile test results are shown in Fig. 2 (engineering stresses and strains are reported). For each mineral concentration, three samples were prepared and tested and the standard deviation of the stiffness and strength was found to be less than 15%. The results show that the incorporation of 8, 16 and 35% of alumina microtablets dramatically increases the stiffness and the strength of the epoxy by factors of 3.8, 8, and 25, and 1.6, 2.5, and 3.9 respectively. This level of improvement can't be seen in other epoxy/alumina composites [3]. The strain at failure and energy absorption however decreased with the inclusion of minerals. The strain however remained uniform within the gage, and localization only appeared at large strains.

5 Finite Element modeling

To predict the tensile behavior of the composite, numerical simulations have been performed on a 2D Representative Volume (RVE, figure 2) of the composite using ABAQUS (version 6.8, MI, United States). The two phases (polymer/tablets) were assumed to be perfectly bonded, and periodic conditions were applied on all boundaries. The RVE was meshed with 4-node quadratic plane strain elements. Tablets were modeled as linear elastic material ($E=300\text{GPa}$, $\nu=0.2$) and epoxy was modeled as Elastic-perfectly plastic material ($E=260\text{MPa}$, $\nu=0.4$, $\sigma_s = 14\text{MP}$). Yielding of the materials was assumed to be governed by Drucker-Prager criterion with pressure sensitivity index of 0.33, in order to capture the cavitation of the polymeric matrix due to tensile hydrostatic stresses. The simulation results were found to be in good agreement with the experiments (Fig. 2). We then used the model to extrapolate the responses of materials with a high mineral content (50vol% and 90vol%). The results indicate that remarkable combinations of stiffness, strength and ductility can

be achieved with this microstructure. We are therefore currently exploring modifications of the doctor blade method enabling higher mineral concentrations.

Fig. 1. SEM image (back-scattered mode) of the cross-section of epoxy/alumina composite, white areas are alumina tablets, dark area is epoxy (scale bar: 100 μm)

Fig. 2. Tensile behavior of epoxy/alumina composites and the simulation results at different mineral concentrations

Acknowledgements

This work has been supported by FQRNT team grant and McGill Engineering Doctoral Award.

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